

A STUDY ON SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING IN MANGALURU CITY-CUSTOMER BENEFITS

Devika*, Bhavya G.**

Final M.com,

Dr P Dayananda Pai-P Sathisha Pai
Government First Grade College, Mangalore

*E-mail: poojarydevika9@gmail.com

**E-mail: ssndipoojary19@gmail.com

Abstract:

Social media is playing a vital role especially in developing countries. It is an emerging source for all companies to create awareness for their products or services in customer minds now a day the majority of the customer in modern days using internet. Social media is one of the ways to give short and eminent information to their target customers and to improve the company sale with the help of Social media companies are share message via the internet through websites, social networks. Social media now a day is among the 'best possibilities available' to an item to get in touch with potential customers. Community social networking websites are the method to interact socially. These new media win the believe in of customers by linking with them at a deeper level. Social media is most important for social networking content sharing and online accessing did to its reliability. Social media opens a wide place for business such as online marketing .marketing which occurs via social media marketing. Social media marketing is a powerful way for businesses of all sizes to reach prospects and customers. Your customers are already interacting with brands through social media, and if you're not speaking directly to your audience through social platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Instagram,

Keywords: social media, growth of internet user. Forms of social media, role of social media techniques of marketing management.

1. INTRODUCTION

Social media marketing is the use of social media platforms and websites to promote a product or service. Although the terms e-marketing and digital marketing are still dominant in academia, social media marketing is becoming more popular for both practitioners and researchers. Most social media platforms have built-in data analytics tools, which enable companies to track the progress, success, and engagement of ad campaigns. Companies address a range of stakeholders through social media marketing, including current and potential customers, current and potential employees, journalists, bloggers, and the general public. On a strategic level, social media marketing includes the management of a marketing campaign, governance, setting the scope (e.g. more active or passive use) and the establishment of a firm's desired social media "culture" and "tone."

When using social media marketing, firms can allow customers and Internet users to post user-generated content (e.g., online comments, product reviews, etc.), also known as "earned media," rather than use marketer-prepared advertising copy. A Social media

networking allow individuals, businesses and other organizations to interact with one another and build relationships and communities online. When companies join these social channels, consumers can interact with them directly. That interaction can be more personal to users than traditional methods of outbound marketing and advertising. Social networking sites act as word of mouth or more precisely, e-word of mouth. The Internet's ability to reach billions across the globe has given online word of mouth a powerful voice and far reach. The ability to rapidly change buying patterns and product or service acquisition and activity to a growing number of consumer's .In 2014, over 80% of business executives identified social media as an integral part of their business and also it is a business strategy. Business retailers have seen 133% increases in their revenues from social media marketing.

2. OBJECTIVE

- To study the benefits to consumer from social media marketing
- To identify what type of strategies are suitable for the company to satisfy the customer.
- To identify the most usable social media in marketing.

3. METHODOLOGY

- Our research study was conducted to know the benefits of customers from the social media marketing reference of Mangalore city. This was done through collection of 50 respondents.
- The research instrument used in collecting data was a questionnaire and survey was conducted through the means of Google form.
- For secondary data other sources like PDF files and internet has been used.

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION:

Table1: Gender wise distribution of sample

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
female	36	71.4
male	14	28.6
total	50	100

As per the above table, 71.4% respondents are female and rest of them 28.6% respondents are male.

Table 2: Age wise distribution of sample

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
	26	52
25-30	19	38
30-35	4	8
35-40	1	2
total	50	100

As per this table, majority of the 52% of the respondents are from 18-25 years of age group, 38% of the respondents are from 25-30 years of age group, 8% of the respondent from 30-35 years of age group, 2% of the respondents are from 35-40 years of age group.

Table 3: qualification wise distribution of sample

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
SSLC	3	6
PUC	5	10
UG	26	52
PG	16	32
total	50	100

As per the above table 50% of respondents are PG qualification, 32% of the respondents are UG qualification, 10% of the respondents are the PUC qualification, 6% of the respondents SSLC qualification.

Table 4: How many time's you use social media?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
once in a week	9	18
Twice in a week	16	32
monthly	21	42
Twice in a month	4	8
total	50	100

As per the above table, 42% of the respondents are monthly using social media, 32% of the respondents are twice in a week using social media, 18% of the respondents are once in a week using the social media, and 8% of the respondents are twice in a month using social media.

Table 5: Which type of social media are you use?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
twitter	6	12
Facebook	14	28
Amazon	10	20
YouTube	14	28
Flipkart	6	12
total	50	100

As per the above table, 12% of the respondents use Twitter, 28% of the respondents use Facebook, 20% of the respondents use Amazon, 28% of respondents use YouTube, and 12% of respondents use Flipkart.

Table 6: What type of benefit you may get in social media marketing?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
access new information	17	34
less cost	12	24
Time consuming	11	22
quick delivery	10	20
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 34% of respondents are says that social media marketing is benefit for access new information, 24% of respondents are says that social media marketing is benefit for less cost , 22% of respondents are says that social media marketing is benefit for time consuming, 20% of respondents are says that social media marketing is benefit forquick delivery.

Table 7:Which type of social media you benefited more in marketing?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
amazon	17	34
Flipkart	17	34
Twitter	16	32
total	50	100

As per the above table, 34% of respondents are benefited more in Amazon marketing, 34% of respondents are benefited in Flipkart marketing, and 32% of respondents are benefited in Twitter Marketing.

Tables 8: Are you agree "social media is backborn of marketing in present scenario"

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Agree	16	32
Strongly agree	30	60
disagree	4	8
Strongly disagree	0	0
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority of 60% of respondents are strongly agree the above statement, 32% of respondents are agree the above statement and rest of the 8% of respondents are disagree the above statement.

Table 9: From which platform do you mostly access your social media accounts for marketing purpose?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Phone	25	50
Laptop	16	32
computer	6	12
tablet	3	6
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 50% of respondents access phone social media accounts for marketing purpose, 32% of respondents access laptop social media accounts for marketing purpose, 12% of respondents access computer social media accounts for marketing purpose remaining, 6% of respondents access tablet social media accounts for marketing purpose.

Table 10: Social media is highly beneficial for marketing purpose?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Yes	42	84
No	8	16
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 84% of respondents are says that yes social media is highly beneficial for marketing purpose and remaining 16% of respondents says that No.

Table 11: Social media helps to improve the business activities?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Yes	40	80
No	10	20
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 80% of exponents are says that social media helps to improve the business activities and rest of the 20% of respondents says that No.

Table 12: Do you think social media marketing is the most effective marketing strategy to attract the consumer?

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
Yes	27	54
No	7	14
Maybe	16	32
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 54% of of respondents says that social media marketing is the most effective marketing strategy to attract the consumer but 32% of responses says that maybe and 14% of responses that No.

Table 13:How much do you agree with this statement " social media marketing helps consumer growth"

Scale	number of respondents	Percentage(%)
agree	29	58
Strongly agree	19	38
disagree	2	4
Strongly disagree	0	0
total	50	100

As per the above table, majority 58% of respondents are agree the above statement, 38% of respondents strongly agree with the above statement and 4% of respondents disagree the above statement.

LIMITATION

- The study was restricted only to the Mangalore city.
- There can be chances of bias in the response given by the respondents.
- The sample size limited to 50 respondents only.

FINDINGS

- The most of the respondent are benefited from the Social media marketing.
- The 80%of respondents are agreed that Social media helps to improve the business activities.
- Most of the respondent says that it is effective marketing strategy to attract the consumer.
- Some of the respondent not agree that social media marketing helps consumer growth.

SUGGESTIONS

- Since social media has become part of everyone's life instead of spending so much money on advertisements, social media is the best platform to promote products.
- Government should encourage social media marketing and must frame rules and regulations.
- Social media is the best source for marketing because a large number of people are using social media.

5. CONCLUSION

This study discussing about benefits to consumers from social media marketing are conducted today in terms of technological, economical, political and cultural exchanges brought about by these forms of modern communication. As we know this modern communication platform giving benefits to customers today. Social media providing big opportunity to organizations to build better relations with clients and providing real one-to-one communication. Customers are now becoming more particular about with whom and from where they are buying products or services. One of the main reasons why businesses must use social media is because their competitors are using this platform daily as a marketing strategy. Customers and future customers also use that. Any products related to social media also help boost the world economy. Products like laptops, iPads, iPhones, headphones, headsets and so on which are used by customers to access social media received very high demand. Social media contains a lot of tools and applications which let the users express their opinion, publish articles, share videos and so on easily. Customers are now becoming more particular about with whom and from where they are buying products or services. They are willing to make an online search before making any purchase decision especially for expensive items. Since the internet is now more conveniently searchable through smartphones, customers can make a search in just a few minutes. That's why companies must have a social media presence and put some attention to manage customers. There is no better advertising than "word of mouth". Satisfied customers surely will share to their friends in their social network about their experiences with a particular company.

6. QUESTIONNAIRE:

"A study on Social Media Marketing in Mangaluru City-Customer benefits"

Name:

Gender: a) Male b) Female

Age:

- 18-25
- 25-30
- 30-35
- 35-40

Educational qualification:

- SSLC
- PUC
- UG
- PG

1. How many times do you use social media?

- Once in a week
 - Twice in a week
 - Monthly
 - Twice in a month
2. Which type of social media you are use?
- Twitter
 - Face book
 - Amazon
 - Flip Kart
3. What type of benefit you may get?
- Quick delivery
 - Time consuming
 - Less cost
 - access new information
4. Which type of social media you benefited more in marketing?
- Amazon
 - Flip kart
 - Twitter
 - Other
5. Are you agree social media is backbone marketing in present scenario?
- Agree
 - Strongly agree
 - Disagree
 - Strongly disagree
6. From which platform do you mostly access your social media accounts for marketing purpose?
- Laptop
 - Phone
 - Tablet
 - Computer
7. Social media is highly beneficial for marketing purpose?
- Yes
 - No
8. Social media helps to improve the business activities?
- Yes
 - No
9. Do you think social media marketing is the most effective marketing strategy to attract the consumer?
- Yes
 - No
 - Maybe
10. How much do you agree with this statement?
“Social media marketing helps consumer growth”

- Agree
- Strongly agree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

7. BIBLIOGRAPHY:

social media marketing. (2019, april 7). Retrieved from yourarticlelibrary:
<https://docs.google.com....om6z0j4>

SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING. (2019, APRIL 6). Retrieved from WIKIPEDIA:
<https://slideshare.net.com>